

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL DEFENCE SERVICE
EXPERTS PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE**

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**РОЗВИТОК ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТІ ФАХІВЦІВ
СЛУЖБИ ЦИВІЛЬНОГО ЗАХИСТУ**

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The article determined the current state training system of civil defense, which points to the need to improve it to comply with modern requirements, the features of the professional competence of specialists civil protection and ways of its development in vocational training. The analysis of scientific and educational research literature on competency approach domestic and foreign scientists who should be considered as a very promising way of closing the gap in education and its inconsistency needs of society. The analysis of psychological and pedagogical sources showed that the problem of professional competence of specialists civil defense scientists studied in the context of the main areas (scientific principles of professional training, disclosing the features of formation of readiness specialist for professional activities on the basis of competence approach, preparation of specialists civil protection). There was show that the professional competence of civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine includes key, basic and special competence. The list of features continuing education are essential for analysis and the formation of professional competence of specialists civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine. These principles are based on professional competence of experts in civil defence during training.

Keywords: competence, professional competence, civil defense, development, experts.

Засоби навчальної та науково-дослідної роботи

У статті схарактеризовано сучасний стан системи підготовки фахівців служби цивільного захисту, який вказує на необхідність її вдосконалення для досягнення відповідності сучасним вимогам, розглянуто особливості професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту та окреслено шляхи її розвитку у системі професійної підготовки. Проведено аналіз науково-педагогічної літератури щодо дослідження компетентнісного підходу вітчизняними та закордонними науковцями який слід розглядати як вельми перспективний шлях ліквідації прогалин у системі освіти та її невідповідності потребам суспільства. Проведений аналіз психолого-педагогічних джерел засвідчив, що проблема розвитку професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту вченими досліджувалася в контексті таких основних напрямів (наукові засади професійної підготовки фахівців; розкриття особливостей формування готовності фахівця до професійної діяльності на засадах компетентнісного підходу; питання підготовки фахівців служби цивільного захисту). З'ясовано що професійна компетентність фахівця служби цивільного захисту ДСНС України включає ключові, базові та спеціальні компетентності. Визначено перелік ознак безперервної освіти, істотних для аналізу і формуванню професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту ДСНС України. Окреслено принципи на яких базується розвиток професійної компетентності фахівців служби цивільного захисту у процесі професійної підготовки.

Ключові слова: компетентність, професійна компетентність, служба цивільного захисту, розвиток, фахівець.

Introduction. The new requirements apply to the quality of vocational training, significantly affected the development of the theory of professional pedagogy, namely the second half of the 1990s. In pedagogical research in Ukraine receives confirmation competence approach. This approach is aimed at enhancing communication education with practice and the real needs of society. Competence is generally the result of education, resulting in the capture of a certain set of human ways of life in relation to a particular object impact.

Search approach to formation of professional competence of experts is currently a large number of researchers: V. Bibik, Ju. Boychuk, V. Yevdokimov, V. Zhuravsky, M. Zgurovsky, A. Pometun, I. Prokopenko et al. This is largely due to the fact that the concept of “competence”, includes a complex, three-dimensional content, integrated professional, social, educational, psychological, legal and other characteristics.

The wording of the article purposes and objectives. The purpose and objectives of the article is in determining the nature and structure of professional competence of civil protection experts and justifying appropriate ways of its development during training.

The main material of the article. At this time in the scientific literature no clear approach to the definition of “professional competence”. In teaching science concept of “professional competence” is regarded as a body of

knowledge and skills that determine the performance of work; the amount of the job skills; combination of personal qualities and properties; complex knowledge and professionally significant personal qualities; vector professionalization; unity of theoretical and practical preparedness for labor; ability to carry out sophisticated operations and others.

In summary, the professional competence as a set of abilities and personality traits necessary for successful professional activity in a given area (I. Zymnaya, W. Slastionin, A. Markova, A. Novikov, N. Kuzmina, Yu. Fokin etc.).

Professional competence comprehensively examines of A. Markova, highlighting its forms: special, social, personal, individual [6].

Experts in the field, both general and vocational education (A. Barannikov [1] S. Batyshev [2] N. Bibik [3] Ju. Boychuk [4], O. Pometun [8] A. Novikov [7], I. Frumin [10] etc.), noted that the use of competency approach should be considered as a very promising way of closing the gap in education and its inconsistency needs of society.

Analysis of psychological and pedagogical sources shows that the problem of professional competence of specialists civil defense scientists studied in the context of the main areas: scientific basis of professional training (N. Abashkina, P. Volovyk, G. Gurevich, V. Evdokimov, I. Zyazyun, A. Kovalenko, N. Nychkalo, M. Lazarev, L. Puhovska, S. Sysoieva, M. Smetansky, P. Yakovyshyna, T. Yatsenko et al.), the disclosure features including the formation of professional readiness for professional activity at basis of competence approach (N. Bibik, Ju. Boychuk, I. Zymnaya, V. Lozova, A. Markova, O. Ovcharuk, O. Pometun, I. Prokopenko, A. Khutorskoi etc.); preparation of civil defence experts (A. Bykov, L. Ishychkina, T. Tkachenko, A. Khrypunov etc.).

In general, the professional competence of of civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine can be understood as an integral professional and personal characteristics of civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine, reflecting the degree of formation of professional knowledge, skills, abilities, skills and willingness to solve problems by application in professional activities, as well as personal of civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine skills to effectively operate in different environments profession. Professional competence of civil defens experts of the SES of Ukraine includes key, basic and special competence.

Key competencies necessary for any professional activity related to the success of the individual in the modern world. Key competencies have now acquired a special significance. They occur primarily in the ability to solve professional tasks through the use of information, communication, social and legal bases of behavior.

Core competencies reflect the specificity of a professional activity (administrative, engineering, etc.).

Special expertise reflecting specifics of a particular subject or nadpredmetni sphere of professional activity. Special competence can be seen as the realization of the key and basic competences in a specific area of professional activity, for example, in fire activity, rescuer.

Key, basic and special expertise in integrating the professional competence of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine, penetrating each other, manifested in the process of solving employee professional tasks of different difficulty levels in different contexts.

One of the major trends of modern education is the widespread adoption of the idea of lifelong learning education throughout life or, as it is even called “lifelong education” – a continuous learning process, training the person who performed consistently in the system of preschool – medium – high – Postgraduate and further education, including retraining and skills.

With this in mind, an analysis of the rationale and ways to implement competency approach to training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine in conjunction with the development and current state of ideas, the concept of lifelong learning.

The analysis shows that in the literature there are three main views on the idea of the lifelong learning:

1) Approach supporters of the “old” origin of the idea of the lifelong learning (A. Darynsky, X. Hummel, G. Yahodin et al.) Who believe that the idea of the lifelong learning, there is as much human society;

2) approach, linking the emergence of the idea of the lifelong learning with the modern era, active processes of spiritual, social, industrial, scientific, technical areas (O. Merchants, Osipov et al.);

3) approach is that although the idea of the lifelong learning for a long time there in pedagogy, the corresponding type of practice has arisen relatively recently (V. Arnaut, A. Vladislavlev, V. Zinchenko, V. Onushkin, N. Sergeev, etc.).

In general, it must be concluded that the analysis of the theoretical foundations of competency approach to training of civil defense experts of the

SES of Ukraine in the context of lifelong learning ideas possible to determine the list of features continuing education are essential for analysis and development of professional competence of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine:

- enrollment (training) all the way to the formation, establishment and development of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine as a professionals;
- the integration of “vertical” (continuity between the different stages, levels of education) and “horizontal” (educational impact of school, family, work collective, informal environment, media, etc.) in the development of professional competence of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine;
- the development and inclusion of an integrated system of education (training) of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine non-institutional and informal forms of education;
- the overall relationship, polytechnic and vocational of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine;
- openness and flexibility of professional training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine;
- a variety of content, tools and methodologies, time and place of study, training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine;
- the possibility of free choice of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine content, tools and methodologies, time and place of retraining and professional development;
- assessment and recognition of education not only on how to obtain it, but the actual result;
- the existence of mechanisms to stimulate the motivation of the individual professional fire and rescue service of the SES of Ukraine to study, improve the professional training of both the material conditions of society, and through the influence of culture (including corporate culture of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine), dominant office and community spiritual and moral values.

The analysis of theoretical assumptions study on improving the professional competence of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine, revealed features of activity at the present stage, the level of knowledge and skills of professionals enrolled in training courses. On this basis must solve the problem of making the original principles training specialists Fire and Rescue Service in the education system of the SES of Ukraine as a system of continuous education.

The main principles on which the system of training identified in P. Hudominskyi scientific work “Development of the training of the teaching staff of the Soviet comprehensive school (1917–1981 hh.)”. We believe that simulation training content is particularly important principles such as [11]:

- the integrity of the content of the training, which is based on the relationship of professional and ideological and political training and expanding the overall outlook unity of theory and practice;
- consistency and continuity of the various levels of training;
- proactive nature of training from the perspectives of development of science and best practices;
- differentiation training content depending on the level of training, work experience and interests of the students individually;
- focus on the use of active methods of training, the full development of their creativity and initiative.

Training principles set forth in these studies, we presented the basic process of organizing training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine. But given the new situation in Ukraine, some advances in psycho-educational science should consider in more detail the basic tenets of training civil protection experts that are trained at the courses of the SES system of Ukraine.

In dictionaries the term “principle” is treated roughly the same: the beginning, the foundation, the basic starting position of any theory, teaching science [9]. Accordingly, we have the task to consider the basic assumptions of the process of training of specialists civil protection in modern conditions. In our country, the existing system of training under the “object” of study (according didactics) typically have specialist professional positive attitudes, stable outlook, motivation and psychological orientation. Therefore, the main task of upgrading system was a task specialist training Lack of knowledge and skills to be applied in the profession. Today anew the question about the value system of training of specialists civil protection due to changes occurring in the country and the system of vocational education.

On the development of professional competence of experts in civil protection training course, this process is in our opinion is based on the following principles: a combination of the individual, society, state and regional peculiarities in training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine; orientation professional training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine integral formation of professional and personal development; accounting professional and personal needs of the content and nature of professional

training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine; integrity of professional training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine; continuity, continuity, character-centered professional training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine; creative and practice-oriented nature of the training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine; providing professional and personal achievements as a result of the improvement of vocational training; individualisation and differentiation process of training experts civil protection; technologization process of professional training of civil defense experts of the SES of Ukraine and the development of their professional competence.

Conclusions. Thus, the study on the professional competence of specialists civil protection in current conditions, the initial level of their professional knowledge, skills and learning the basic trends of the preparation process allow to improve the scientific and methodological support of professional competence.

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